

Maternal and Fetal Outcomes of Antenatal Patients with Thyroid Dysfunction in Tertiary Health Care Centre of Central India- A Trimester Wise Study

P Rohini¹, Akansha Parihar², Pallavi Pathak³, Manali Chawla⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MGMMC and MTH Hospital, Indore

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Corresponding Author: Dr. P. Rohini

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Abstract:

Introduction: There is significant changes in thyroid gland in pregnancy. Numerous outcomes for the mother and the foetus are impacted by maternal thyroid problems. Preterm labour, abruptio placenta, abortion, and pre-eclampsia are the main obstetric complications, whereas prematurity, low birth weight, stillbirth, and perinatal mortality are the main foetal issues. Untreated mothers have a significant impact on their offspring's future intellectual development.

Objective: To study the maternal and fetal outcomes of antenatal women with deranged thyroid functions.

Methodology: All antenatal pregnant females coming in MYH antenatal OPD in their first trimester reporting to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, MGM Medical College and MY hospital, Indore were included in this study. The patients having deranged thyroid profile (S.TSH level- >2.5ug/dl) were followed up for all the three trimester till delivery.

Result: A total of 300 cases were studied. In present study majority of the women were euthyroid (60%), followed by 30% of women with sub-clinical hypothyroidism and 6.3% with hypothyroidism. The most common maternal complication were preterm labor and PIH. Majority of the newborn with low birth weight, NICU admission, Meconium stained liquor and respiratory distress belong to sub-clinical hypothyroid mothers.

Conclusion: Maternal thyroid dysfunction is associated with significant adverse effects on maternal and fetal outcome emphasizing the importance of routine antenatal thyroid screening in first trimester.

Keywords: Pregnancy, Subclinical Hypothyroidism, Outcomes, Hyperthyroidism.

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Introduction

Pregnancy has a significant impact on thyroid physiology and thyroid disorders are among the most prevalent endocrine disorders. There are significant regional differences in the prevalence of thyroid problems during pregnancy. According to literature, the prevalence of hypothyroidism during pregnancy is 2.5%, while that of hyperthyroidism during pregnancy ranges from 0.1% to 0.4% [8].

The two primary clinical types of hypothyroidism. Overt hypothyroidism is defined by an elevated serum TSH and subnormal free thyroxine (FT4), while subclinical hypothyroidism is characterised by an elevated serum TSH and normal free thyroxine (FT4). Cases of subclinical hypothyroidism, affects 2.3% of pregnant women, overt hypothyroidism is detected in 0.2% of cases [1]. Numerous outcomes for the mother and the foetus are impacted by maternal thyroid problems. Preterm labour, abruptio placenta, abortion, and pre-eclampsia are the main obstetric complications, whereas prematurity, low birth weight, stillbirth, and perinatal mortality are the main foetal issues.

Untreated mothers have a significant impact on their offspring's future intellectual development. Children born to hypothyroid moms have experienced negative prenatal and postnatal outcomes, including attention deficit and hyperactivity syndrome [2]. There might be foetal growth retardation as a result of hyperthyroidism during pregnancy, which is primarily caused by Grave's disease.

Due to large number of physiologic alterations in thyroid functioning, the typical reference range of thyroid hormones in pregnant women has been the subject of numerous investigations. The ethnicity, geographic location, iodine status, rigor for selection of reference population and estimating method all affect these values, though [3]. Thus, it is crucial to establish reference intervals for each trimester of pregnancy. Thyroid abnormalities should be diagnosed using these values during pregnancy. Thyroid levels for each trimester must be established for various populations around the world since reference intervals must be

demographic, technique, and gestational age specific. There are few data on trimester-specific thyroid hormone levels during pregnancy in India, and none from Madhya Pradesh.

Methods

- Permission from the institutional ethics committee and university clearance was obtained.
- Meeting and rapport building with the study participants.
- All antenatal pregnant females coming in MYH antenatal OPD in their first trimester reporting to the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, MGM Medical College and MY hospital, Indore were included in this study.
- The patients were provided with the study information sheet and consent form and were explained about the relevant details about the study in a language best understood by them.
- Informed written consent was obtained after explaining about the purpose, nature and process of the study and then data collection was started.
- Prestructured, pretested proforma was used to collect details about the patients.
- Demographic profile, detailed history, risk factors, physical and obstetrics examination including general physical, abdominal and pelvic examination were noted.
- Baseline T3, T4 and S. TSH was done. Patients with deranged thyroid function were started on medications according to standard protocol.
- Investigation details such as complete haemogram, thyroid profile, viral markers, urine routine microscopy, USG, Ante-natal profile were also noted.
- These patients were followed up for 3 trimesters Antenatal and intra-natal details were noted.
- Maternal and foetal monitoring was performed according to standard guidelines.

- Maternal and foetal outcome in terms of morbidity and mortality were noted.

Data Analysis: Data was collected and entered simultaneously in statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23 and coded appropriately. The data was analysed keeping in view the aim and objectives of the study. Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the sample characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage. Graphs and Charts were made. Analytical and inferential analysis was done. Significant was set at standard 0.05.

Ethical Clearance: The research described was approved from the Ethical Committee of MGM Medical College, Indore and was conducted with approved guidance and regulations. Written informed consent was taken from the patient.

All the study participants were explained in detail about the purpose of the study in their own language which they could understand.

Results and Observation

In this study, most of the study participants belongs to the age group of 18 – 25 years of age; 36.7%, followed by 33.3% 26 – 30 years of age group, 31-35 years of age group consists of 16.3% of participants, 7.3% and 6.3% of participants belongs to 36 – 40 years and > 40 years of age group respectively. Mean age of the participants was 28± 6.

Minimum age was 18 years and maximum age was 42 years. As per Modified Kuppuswamy scale, Most of the study participants i.e; 68% belongs to the lower middle and upper lower class of the society, 17% belongs to the lower class, 9.7% belongs to upper middle class and only 5.3% belongs to upper class of the society. 52.3% of the study participants were normal weight, 41.7% were overweight and obese, and 6% were underweight.

Table 1: Distribution of study participants according to baseline characteristics

Base line characteristics		Count	Column N %
Age Group	18 - 25 years	110	36.7%
	26 - 30 years	100	33.3%
	31 - 35 years	49	16.3%
	36 - 40 years	22	7.3%
	> 40 years	19	6.3%
Socio-economic Status	Upper Class	16	5.3%
	Upper Middle Class	29	9.7%
	Lower Middle Class	91	30.3%
	Upper Lower Class	113	37.7%
	Lower Class	51	17.0%
Body Mass Index (Kg/m ²)	< 18.5 Underweight	18	6.0%
	18.5-24.9 Normal Weight	157	52.3%
	25-29.9 Overweight	110	36.7%
	30-34.9 Obese Class I	15	5.0%

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Age	28	6
Height	58	7
Weight	1.55	.06
Body Mass Index (Kg/m2)	24.09	3.47
Systolic Blood Pressure	120	6
Diastolic Blood Pressure	80	6

In this study, 60% of the study participants were Euthyroid, 30% of the participants were subclinical hypothyroid, 6.3% had Hypothyroidism, 3% had subclinical hyperthyroidism and only 0.7% of the participants were hyperthyroid.

Table 2: Distribution of study participants according to diagnosis

Diagnosis	Count	Column N %
Euthyroid	180	60.0%
Hypothyroidism	19	6.3%
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	90	30.0%
Hyperthyroidism	2	0.7%
Subclinical Hyperthyroidism	9	3.0%

Figure 1: Distribution of study participants according to diagnosis

Table 3: Comparison and association of High risk factors and deranged thyroid profile.

	Diagnosis										Total	p Value
	Euthyroid		Hypothyroidism		Subclinical Hypothyroidism		Hyperthyroidism		Subclinical Hyperthyroidism			
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %		
Primi Gravida	67	55.4 %	8	6.6%	42	34.7 %	0	0.0%	4	3.3%	54	.03*
Multi Gravida	101	61.2 %	11	6.7%	48	29.1 %	2	1.2%	3	1.8%	64	

Grand Multi Gravida	12	85.7 %	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	14.3%	2	
History of Irregular Mensus	10	30.3 %	4	12.1 %	17	51.5 %	0	0.0%	2	6.1%	23	0.00
History of Infertility	4	40.0 %	1	10.0 %	5	50.0 %	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	6	0.61
Oligohydramnios	5	25.0 %	2	10.0 %	12	60.0 %	0	0.0%	1	5.0%	15	0.02
Abruption	3	37.5 %	2	25.0 %	3	37.5 %	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	5	0.22
Mean BMI	22.57 ± 2.78		26.67 ± 2.41		26.99 ± 2.5		18.45 ± 1.06		21.17 ± 3.76		0.02	

Above table explains that 55.4% of the primigravida participants were Euthyroid, 34.7% were subclinical hypothyroid 6.6% were hypothyroid and 3.3% were subclinical hyperthyroid. 61.2% of multigravida were euthyroid, 29.1% were Subclinical hypothyroid 6.7% had hypothyroidism and 1.8% were subclinical hyperthyroid. 85.71% of grand multigravida participants were euthyroid and 14.29% were hyperthyroid.

History of irregular menses were mostly associated with subclinical hypothyroid participants and it was statistical significant. History of infertility were mostly associated with subclinical hypothyroid

participants but it was not statistical significant. Oligohydramnios were mostly associated with subclinical hypothyroid participants and it was statistical significant. History of Miscarriage were mostly associated with subclinical hypothyroid participants and it was statistical significant.

On comparison of mean BMI among participants with Euthyroid, Hypo , subclinical hypothyroidism hyperthyroidism and subclinical hyperthyroidism, it was found that mean BMI of hypothyroid patients and subclinical hypothyroid was higher than the other groups and it was found to be statistical significant.

Figure 2: Comparison and association of High risk factors and thyroid profile

This table explains thyroid profile and maternal complications, it was found that Preterm, PIH, Abruptions and PPH were found to be mostly associated with Subclinical hypothyroidism. PIH were found to be statistical significant.

Table 4: Comparison of maternal outcome with thyroid dysfunction

Maternal Complications	Diagnosis										Total	P Value
	Euthyroid		Hypothyroidism		Subclinical Hypothyroidism		Hyperthyroidism		Subclinical Hyperthyroidism			
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %		
Preterm	6	31.6 %	2	10.5 %	10	52.6 %	0	0.0%	1	5.3%	19	0.12
PIH	7	33.3 %	2	9.5%	12	57.1 %	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	21	0.05
Abruption	3	37.5 %	2	25.0 %	3	37.5 %	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	8	0.22
Post-Partum Haemorrhage	4	44.4 %	2	22.2 %	3	33.3 %	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	9	0.34

Figure 3: Comparison and association of Thyroid profile and maternal complications

Below table explains thyroid profile and foetal complications, it was found that Low birth weight, NICU Admission and MSL were found to be mostly associated with Subclinical hypothyroidism. All above variables were found to be statistical significant.

Table 5: Comparison and association of foetal outcomes and thyroid complications

Foetal outcomes	Diagnosis										Total	P Value
	Euthyroid		Hypothyroidism		Subclinical Hypothyroidism		Hyperthyroidism		Subclinical Hyperthyroidism			
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %		
Low Birth Weight	37	39.4 %	10	10.6%	41	43.6%	2	2.1%	4	4.3%	94	0.000*
NICU admission	44	55.0 %	7	8.8%	27	33.8%	1	1.3%	1	1.3%	80	0.135

n												
MSL	2	20.0%	3	30.0%	5	50.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	10	0.003*
Respiratory Distress	33	51.6%	9	14.1%	21	32.8%	0	0.0%	1	1.6%	64	0.006*

Figure 4: Comparison and association of Thyroid profile and foetal complications

Discussion

In present study majority of the women were euthyroid (60%), followed by 30% of women with sub-clinical hypothyroidism and 6.3% with hypothyroidism. Also 3% of the women had sub-clinical hyperthyroidism and 0.7% with hyperthyroidism. Presence of goitrogens in diet, micronutrient deficiency such as selenium and iron deficiency may cause hypothyroidism. Poverty, insufficient iodine supplementation and fluorinated water may be the major cause for thyroid disorder among pregnant women.

Baseline Characteristics: In present study, majority of the ante natal women reporting were in the age group of 18-25 years (36.7%) followed by 26-30 years (33.3%). Mean age of the study participants was 28±6 years. These findings are consistent with the fact that marriages and child bearing is in early age in our country. Gupta et al [4] in their study reported that mean age among study participants was 31.30±4.92years. Meena et al in their study reported that majority of the study participants were in the age group of 20-25 years followed by 26-30 years. Majority of the study

participants belonged to lower class. Gupta et al [4] in their study also reported similar results.

On observing BMI of all the ante natal women, it was observed that majority of the pregnant women had normal BMI (18.5-24.9). 6% of the women were underweight, 36% were overweight and 5% had obesity class I. Mean BMI among study participants was 24.09±3.47 Kg/m². Gupta et al [4] in their study reported that majority of the women had BMI between > 30 Kg/m².

Deranged thyroid profile: In present study majority of the women were euthyroid (60%), followed by 30% of women with sub-clinical hypothyroidism and 6.3% with hypothyroidism. Also 3% of the women had sub-clinical hyperthyroidism and 0.7% with hyperthyroidism. Presence of goitrogens in diet, micronutrient deficiency such as selenium and iron deficiency may cause hypothyroidism. Poverty, insufficient iodine supplementation and fluorinated water may be the major cause for thyroid disorder among pregnant women. Gupta et al [4] in their study reported that prevalence of sub-clinical hypothyroidism was found to be 5.50% and overt

hypothyroidism as 0.92% while subclinical hyperthyroidism was observed as 3.12% and 0.81% overt hyperthyroidism. Gayatri R et al [5] also reported that hypothyroidism was much more common than hyperthyroidism.

Sarladevi R et al [6] in their study reported that prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism, overt hypothyroidism, subclinical hyperthyroidism and overt hyperthyroidism is 6.4%, 2.8%, 1.8% and 0.6% respectively. Das et al [7] in their study reported that 61.70% were detected with hypothyroidism and 1.02% with hyperthyroidism.

Maternal Complications: In our study the maternal complications observed in different thyroid dysfunction and majority of patients were preterm delivery, PIH, Abruptio placentae and PPH. The association was found to be statistically significant for preterm delivery and PIH. Maternal complications were most commonly associated with sub-clinical hypothyroid mothers. There were increased cases of preterm delivery, preeclampsia and postpartum haemorrhage in cases of subclinical hypothyroidism that hypothyroidism.

None of the maternal complications were seen with hyperthyroid mothers. Similar to our findings, Saraladevi R et al [8] in their study reported that subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy is associated with the complications like preeclampsia (9.37%), Abruptio placentae (1.56%) and preterm delivery (7.81%). Similarly according to Swathi et al [9] subclinical hypothyroidism was associated with complications like preeclampsia (24%), Abruptio placentae (1%), anaemia (12.5%), AB (4.8%), Post-partum haemorrhage (1.9%) and preterm delivery (8.65%).

Whereas Gupta et al [4] in their study reported that association was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) in pre-eclampsia, IUGR and abruptio placenta. Chouhan et al [10] in their study reported that maternal complication among overt Hypothyroidism was associated with Preeclampsia (18.7%), Abruptio placentae (6.25%), Pre term delivery (12.5%) and Severe Anaemia (31.25%).

Pregnancy and foetal complications: Thyroid disorders have a significant influence over metabolic and physiological activities and hence these eventually affect the maternal and fetal wellbeing. In present study, majority of the still born, IUGR and abortions were seen with antenatal women with sub clinical hypothyroidism. Also, statistically significant association was found between pregnancy outcomes (baby status at birth, IUGR and Abortions) with deranged thyroid profile. Sarkar D et al [11] found that minimal degree of hypothyroidism can increase the rate of miscarriage and fetal death and can be an underlying aetiology of recurrent pregnancy loss. Meena et al [12] in their study reported that

significant prevalence of IUGR, low birth weight, neonatal morbidity and mortality in patients of pregnancy with thyroid disorder (9.18%, 13.26%, 14.28% and 7.14% respectively).

Reduced fetal thyroxine may cause disruption to the development of the pituitary-thyroid axis of the newborn, fetal pituitary growth hormone secretion, vascular responsiveness and maturation, and cardiovascular homeostasis in utero. These factors are causative for the observation of reduced neonatal birth weight of offspring born to mothers with inadequately controlled hypothyroidism.

In present study, significant association was found between foetal complications and deranged thyroid profile. Majority of the newborn with low birth weight, NICU admission, Meconium stained liquor and respiratory distress belong to mothers with sub clinical hypothyroidism 54.26% babies with low birth weight were born to hypothyroid women compared to 39.36% babies born to euthyroid women. Gupta et al [4] in their study reported that complications like Low birth weight, Hyperbilirubinemia and NICU admission were having statistically significant association with deranged thyroid profile.

Chouhan et al [12] in their study reported that among sub-clinical hypothyroidism cases, 3.75% were IUGR, 3.75% were still born and 10.75% were low birth weight. Saraladevi R et al [6] in their study reported that subclinical hypothyroidism in pregnancy is associated with the complications like IUGR (6.25%), low birth weight (4.68%) and still birth (1.56%). Swathi et al [13] in their study reported that subclinical hypothyroidism was associated with foetal complications like IUGR (13.46%), respiratory distress (27.88%), IUD (1.92%).

Maurya et al [14] found out that Out of 41 patients with thyroid dysfunction, foetal complications seen were hyperbilirubinemia (12.2%), Foetal distress (4.88%), NICU admission (17.07%) and low birth weight (21.95%).

Summary

Salient results of the study are summarized below-

1. In present study majority of the study participants were in the age group of 18-25 years.
2. Majority of the study participants belonged to lower class.
3. Majority of the study participants had BMI with in normal range.
4. Majority of the pregnant women in the present study had sub-clinical hypothyroidism who were not on any medications.
5. On analysing obstetric risk factors, it was found that Parity, history of irregular menses, oligohydramnios, history of miscarriage and

BMI was found to be statistically associated with deranged thyroid profile.

6. Majority of the still born, IUGR and abortions were seen with antenatal women with sub-clinical hypothyroidism. Also, statistically significant association was found between pregnancy outcomes with deranged thyroid profile.
7. In present study, significant association was found between foetal complications and deranged thyroid profile. Majority of the newborn with low birth weight, NICU admission, Meconium stained liquor and respiratory distress belong to sub-clinical hypothyroid mothers.
8. In our study the maternal complications observed in different thyroid dysfunction and majority of patients were preterm delivery, PIH, Abruptio placentae and PPH. The association was found to be statistically significant for preterm delivery and PIH. Maternal complications were most commonly associated with mothers with sub-clinical hypothyroidism.

Conclusion

In our study sub-clinical hypothyroidism was the most common thyroid disorder found in pregnant women. Thyroid problems significantly alter metabolic and physiological processes, which in turn have an impact on the health of the mother and foetus. In subclinical hypothyroidism, pregnant women with TSH level >10m IU/L and women with TSH level 4-10m IU/L with positive TPOAb status must always be treated. Pregnant women with TSH level 4-10 m IU/L with TPOAb negative status can be considered for treatment. However, there is limited studies on pregnant women with TSH between 2.5 to 4 m IU/L which was the basis of this research. Therefore, it should be thought of universally screening expectant women for thyroid disorders, especially in a nation like India where there is a high prevalence of undetected thyroid disorders. Our study has a lot of advantages as it adds to the body of knowledge by reporting observed TSH, T4 and T3 readings in all three trimesters of pregnancy. The strong correlation between various fetomaternal unfavourable outcomes and hypothyroidism further emphasizes the need for routine thyroid function testing throughout pregnancy.

References

1. Singh A, Reddy M. Prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in pregnancy and its implications. *Int J Med Sci Public Heal*. 2015; 4(9):1247.
2. Das D, Salman Chisty SJ, Barman K. Prevalence of thyroid disorders among pregnant women in lower Assam. *New Indian J OBGYN*. 2021; 7(2):202–5. .
3. Kulhari K, Negi R, Kalra DK, Paul SK. Establishing Trimester-Specific Reference Ranges for Thyroid Hormones in Indian Women with Normal Pregnancy: New Light through Old Window. *Int J Contemp Med Res [IJCMR]*. 2019; 6(4):4–7. .
4. Gupta P, Jain M, Gupta NK, Gupta UK. The Study of Maternal and Fetal Outcome in Pregnant Women with Thyroid Disorder: a Prospective Study in Indore Region. *Indian J Appl Res*. 2021; (August 2021):69–71. .
5. Gayathri R, Lavanya S RK. Subclinical hypothyroidism and autoimmune thyroiditis in pregnancy—A study in south Indian subjects. *J Assoc Physicians India*. 2009; 57:691–3. .
6. Rama Saraladevi. Prevalence of Thyroid Disorder in Pregnancy. *Int J Tech Res Appl*. 2016; 4(2):2320–8163.
7. Das D, Salman Chisty SJ, Barman K. Prevalence of thyroid disorders among pregnant women in lower Assam. *New Indian J OBGYN*. 2021; 7(2):202–5. .
8. Swati et al. Clinical study of thyroid dysfunction in pregnant women and its effect on maternal and fetal outcome. *MedPulse Int J Gynaecol*. 2019; 12(3):71–6. .
9. Manisha Chouhan et al. Thyroid Dysfunction and Pregnancy Outcome in Indian Women. *J Med Sci Clin Res*. 2016; 04(03):10666–71. .
10. Sakar D et al, Recurrent pregnancy loss in patients with thyroid dysfunction. *Indian J Endocrinol Metab*. 2012; 16(02):350–1.
11. Meena DS, Bhati I, Bora S, Meena S. Original Research Article Study of Thyroid Dysfunction in Pregnancy. *Int J Curr Microbiol Applies Sci*. 2015; 4(9):91–7. .
12. Swati et al. Clinical study of thyroid dysfunction in pregnant women and its effect on maternal and fetal outcome. *MedPulse Int J Gynaecol*. 2019; 12(3):71–6. .
13. 14. Al Maurya et al. The study of maternal and foetal outcome in pregnant women with thyroid disorder. *Int J Reprod Contraception, Obstet Gynecol*. 2019; 8(5):69–71.